

The rhetoric of complaint: a cross-cultural study of online discourse

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Abstract

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How do people complain online? Recent research on the question has focused on hotel reviews, and on basic features such as positive and negative evaluative comments, and references to expectations (Vásquez, 2011), finding substantial variation in linguistic and semantic features, ratings, sentiment, and usefulness (Xiang et. al. 2017), and how specific online platform affordances affect the degree of review negativity (Ruytenbeek et. al., 2021). Hospitality is just one sector, however, and research on complaints in airline reviews (e.g., Rita et. al. 2022) has focused on the effects on industry, not the linguistic elements of complaints themselves. Research in both domains has focused on complaints in English, rather than other linguacultures. We present a computational-linguistic study of over 15,000 airline reviews on TripAdvisor between 2016 and 2022. In collecting data from both flagship and budget carriers in Canada (AirCanada, AirTransat), Nigeria (Arik, Air Peace), and Japan (Japan Airlines, Peach Aviation), our research questions were: (1) The genre of complaints ranges from expressions of frustration and disappointment to allegations of injustice, abuse, and emotional harm. What can linguistic features reveal about this spectrum? (2) How do consumers from these cultures make use of the genre? Using word frequency analysis and topic modeling, we found emotional expression and moral concepts varied by country, culture, and airline. (Im)politeness was the target of more complaints about Canadian airlines, while the interpersonal conduct of airline staff dominated complaints about Nigerian carriers, and disappointed expectations were reflected in a relatively higher percentage of negative reviews for Japanese airlines. Many negative reviews adopted extreme case

formulations (Pomerantz, 1986), possibly as a way to seek compensation from the airlines. Other reviews seem to function as public displays of disappointment and exasperation, without a compensation-seeking goal per se.

Slides

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